

The ever-increasing silent menace of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance: a global perspective

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Abstract:

The alarming status of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance (PMQR), with its increasing prevalence across several bacterial species worldwide, should be a significant public health concern. PMQR genes like *qnr*, *aac(6')-Ib-cr*, *qepA*, & *oqxAB* were detected in various pathogens, indicating a widespread dissemination of resistance mechanisms. The widespread occurrence of PMQR poses significant challenges for public health and the development of new antimicrobial therapies. This resistance mechanism facilitates the rapid dissemination and spread of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) across bacterial populations, thereby complicating treatment options and increasing healthcare costs. Hence, there is an urgent need for ongoing surveillance and strategic measures to lessen the effects of PMQR through the application of One Health approach.

Keywords: Plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance, antimicrobial resistance, antibiotic susceptibility, foodborne pathogens, human–animal interface, One Health, Preventive healthcare

Introduction:

Quinolones, a large class of antibiotics, frequently used to treat infections brought on by both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, which includes *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Quinolone resistance can either be intrinsic, where wild-type bacteria display naturally occurring resistance to specific antimicrobial agents, or acquired, which is a result of genetic mutations that might modify the molecular targets of quinolones (i.e., DNA gyrase & topoisomerase IV), or promote expression that codes for efflux pumps [1]. Plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance (PMQR) refers to the capability of bacteria to resist the effects of quinolone antibiotics through mechanisms encoded by genes found on plasmids, which are tiny, round DNA fragments that bacteria can exchange through Horizontal Gene Transfer (HGT). In 1998, PMQR was initially discovered in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* obtained at the University of Alabama. This bacteria could transmit low-level resistance to a number of quinolones, including ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid, to various Gram-negative bacterial species. Thereafter, transmissible PMQR genes have been reported from countries worldwide including China [3-5], India [6-8], Bangladesh [9], Japan [10-11], Taiwan [12], Australia [13], France [14-15], Germany [16-17], UK [18], Canada [19], Netherlands [20], Belgium [21], Denmark [22], Mexico [23], Columbia [24], Argentina [25], Tunisia [26], and Senegal [27].

The most well-known form of PMQR is through the *qnr* genes (viz., *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrC*, *qnrD*, *qnrS*, *qnrVC*) that probably originate in aquatic bacteria, and code for pentapeptide repeat proteins shield topoisomerase IV and DNA gyrase against quinolone inhibition [28, 29]. Alternatively, certain quinolones can be enzymatically inactivated by a particular aminoglycoside acetyltransferase, *aac(6′)-Ib-cr*, or plasmid-encoded quinolone efflux pumps like *qepA* and *oqxAB* [30]. Although plasmid-transmitted resistance mechanisms alone may not surpass the clinical threshold for susceptibility, they might facilitate the concomitant selection of some other more harmful resistance genes, thereby making infections from pathogens bearing PMQR genes more persistent and difficult to treat.

PMQR is also a major cause of concern in case of foodborne pathogens and transmission of AMR at the human–animal interface, as per reports from Morocco [31] and Chile [32], thus highlighting the significance of the One Health Approach in preventive healthcare [33].

Mechanisms of PMQR:

Plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance (PMQR) involves several well-described resistance mechanisms against quinolone antibiotics [28-30, 34-39], as represented in **Figure 1**. These mechanisms are primarily facilitated by genes carried on plasmids and can be summarised as follows:

(i) Target Protection due to expression of Qnr Proteins:

Genes like *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrC*, *qnrD*, *qnrS*, or *qnrVC* encode the Qnr proteins, which belong to the pentapeptide repeat family. The actions of quinolone antibiotics are opposed by these proteins, which stop them from inhibiting bacterial DNA gyrase or topoisomerase IV.

(ii) Drug Modification by Acetyltransferase:

The enzyme *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* alters quinolones by acetylating their piperazinyl substituent. This modification reduces the drug activity, particularly in ciprofloxacin and other fluoroquinolones.

(iii) Efflux Pumps:

Quinolones are actively expelled from bacterial cells by plasmid-encoded efflux pumps like *qepA* and *oqxAB*, which lowers their intracellular concentration and effectiveness.

Detection of PMQR:

PMQR genes in bacterial isolates are detected utilizing various molecular approaches, with the primary goal being identifying particular resistance genes. The most popular techniques are those based on WGS, PCR, & MIC testing. Although conventional PCR is widely used to identify PMQR genes in clinical isolates, multiplex PCR allows simultaneous detection of multiple PMQR genes, enhancing efficiency in identifying co-carriage of resistance genes in isolates [40]. Alternatively, the Agar Dilution method determines the MIC of quinolones, providing insight into the resistance level [41]. At the same time, Conjugation experiments help evaluate the transmissibility of PMQR genes, indicating their potential spread among bacterial populations [42].

Figure 1: Diagrammatic representation of the most common mechanisms involved in plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance.

PMQR and gut microbiome:

AMR research has generally been more attentive to clinically relevant pathogenic bacteria, and largely ignored the potentially vast pool of resistance genes that might exist in non-pathogenic bacteria present in the environment, or in the commensal bacteria constituting the human microflora [43]. The human gut microbiota, with its high density of microorganisms and high accessibility to numerous bacteria from the environment, presents ideal conditions for harbouring a variety of antimicrobial resistance elements acquired through HGT [44].

The World Health Organization (WHO) has reported 85–90% incidence of antibiotic resistance in gut-resident commensal bacteria like *E. coli* & *K. pneumoniae*, which may often act as reservoirs of AMR genes, and either themselves turn pathogenic, or spread these genes among *Shigella*, *Salmonella*, and other harmful Enterobacterales [45, 46]. Thus, treatment choices for *shigellosis* and *salmonellosis*, two intestinal illnesses are seriously compromised by quinolone resistance, since fluoroquinolones are generally the drug of choice for Enterobacterales infections [47]. In fact, a recent study from Poland has found that PMQR-positive Enterobacterales isolates are responsible for the development of infections in men undergoing transrectal prostate biopsy, since fluoroquinolones are generally prescribed as prophylaxis in these cases [48]. Fluoroquinolone resistant organisms were also found in a significant proportion of rectal swab samples from male patients undergoing ultrasound guided transrectal prostate biopsy in the United States [49].

A whole metagenome sequencing survey in the Korean population to detect ARGs in the stool of 61 healthy subjects with ages between 30-59 years, has revealed that 59% were PMQR-

positive and 83% carried 2–4 PMQR genes [50]. There has also been reports of European travelers acquiring substantial PMQR after visiting Southeast Asia and India [51].

Methods:

PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) was used as its primary resource for searching the relevant articles using keywords/search terms like “plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance”/ “PMQR gut microbiome” etc. Supplementary **Table S1** contains a list of articles discussed in the next section of this review, while **Figure 2** shows a representative diagram of the global distribution of these articles.

Discussion:

PMQR in India:

A recent study on PMQR genes present in environmental samples found that 24.59% among the kinds of *E. coli* that were recovered from the Yamuna, one of the biggest rivers in northern India, carried the PMQR gene *qnrS1* [52]. Another cross-sectional study on foods of animal origin (egg, milk, fish, chicken), both raw & cooked, collected from different street food vendors at different localities of two North Indian cities, Delhi and Bareilly, between September 2015 to May 2017, detected *qnrB* in 14%, and *qnrS* in 78.6%, in its *E. coli* isolates [53]. There is also a very recent report from Kolkata about seven isolates of *Pantoea agglomerans*, a species that does not generally infect humans, being recovered from patients suffering from bacteremia, in the time-period between March to October 2022, carrying the PMQR genes *qnrB* and *qnrS* [54].

PMQR in other Asian countries:

In 2016, a large-scale study on 755 foodborne *Salmonella* isolates from 26 provinces of mainland China, identified in *Salmonella* Derby CFSA231, four PMQR genes—*aac(6′)-Ib-cr*, *qnrS2*, *oqxA*, *oqxB*—are located in a 64 kb area that resembles a *Salmonella* genomic island (SGI) [55]. Another study identified *Salmonella enterica* serotype Indiana (*S. Indiana*), a ciprofloxacin & cefotaxime (CIP-CTX) co-resistant bacterium, possesses the PMQR *aac(6′)-Ib-cr*, *oqxA*, *oqxB*, recovered from poultry flesh obtained from seven locations in six Chinese

provinces between August 2010 and March 2012 [56]. Furthermore, seven PMQR genes have been identified in a comprehensive AMR genomic characterization of 238 (67.6%) *Salmonella* 4,[5],12:i:-isolates collected in Guangdong province, China, spanning a ten-year period (2009–2019) [57]. Among its contents were *oqxAB* (n = 123), *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* (n = 72), *qnrS* (n = 100), *qnrVC* (n = 1), *qnrA* (n = 1), *qnrB* (n = 1), and *qnrD* (n = 1). Six PMQR genes have been identified in 334 *Salmonella* isolates from 6,223 rectal swabs of pets in Chongqing, China: *qnrS* (18.9%), *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* (16.5%), *qnrA* (4.8%), *qnrB* (4.2%), *qnrD* (0.9%), and *oqxAB* (1.5%) [58]. Similarly, a surveillance of *Escherichia coli* isolated from fecal samples of 367 healthy chickens belonging to 6 farms located in Shandong Province, China, during 2009–2014, also revealed the presence of PMQR genes like *qnrS* (29.62%), *qnrC* (3.52%), *qnrD* (0.88%), *oqxAB* (27%), and *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* (30.79%), implying that *E. coli* from healthy chickens could also become a potential reservoir of PMQRs [59].

The first report of the *qepA* gene detected in Bangladesh came from a study on 19 *E. coli* (n = 12) & *K. pneumoniae* (n = 7) environmental isolates, where four of each were found to carry *qnrS*, and a single *E. coli* isolate harboured a new variant of *qepA* [60]. Another study reported that PMQR-genes were present in almost 66% among the 300 *E. coli* isolates in wastewater samples collected in 2017 and 2018 from houses (n = 80), ponds (n = 71), live-bird markets (n = 74), or rivers (n = 75) in Bangladesh's urban and rural areas [61]. *qnrS* was the most prevalent gene among them (82%, n = 164), with *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* (9%), *oqxAB* (7%), *qnrB* (6%), & *qepA* (4%), following in order.

Similar reports have originated from Thailand, where the PMQR genes 113 *E. coli* isolates found in it have been determined to be in Namsuay watershed in upper northeastern Thailand, surface water, wastewater, or discharge water may contain *aac(6′)-Ib-cr*, *qepA*, or *oqxAB* [62]. 10.1% of *Salmonella enterica* isolates in Thailand between 2016 and 2019 collected from pet dogs (n = 159) and cats (n = 19), were found to carry the PMQR gene *qnrS* as part of an inquiry into the AMR status of these bacteria [63]. In a different study involving 791 *E. coli* isolates, 56.4% of 601 samples from animal food products such as beef, poultry, pig, milk, and eggs, as well as rectal swabs from swine farms and environmental samples from farms and slaughterhouses in the Philippines, had the *qnrA1*, *qnrB4*, and *qnrS1* genes [64].

90% in *E. coli* or 100% of *K. pneumoniae* isolates with UTIs in Azerbaijan, Iran, had PMQR genes such as *qnrA* (1.7%), *qnrB* (28.3%), *qnrC* (1.7%), *qnrD* (16.7%), *qnrS* (21.7%), *qepA* (5.0%), *oqxA* (36.7%), *oqxB* (51.7%), and *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* (71.7%) [65]. Similar findings were made with the high frequencies of PMQR genes, especially *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* (92.5%), *qnrB* (51.8%), *qepA* (40.7%), or *qnrS* (37%), in *K. pneumoniae* isolates from Baghdad, Iraq [66]. Additionally, 41 out of 107 clinical *E. coli* isolates in Saudi Arabian patients had *QnrS* and *aac(6′)-Ib-cr* incorporated in them [67].

PMQR in African countries:

Abubakar et al. recently conducted a comprehensive review on the prevalence of PMQR genes in Enterobacteriales in Africa, which included 32 articles from West and North Africa and only one article reporting a study conducted in Central Africa, genes *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrC*, *qnrD*, *qnrS*, *aac(6′)Ib*, *aac(6′)Ib-cr*, *oqxAB*, and *qepA* were found [68]. The most common gene was *aac(6′)Ib-cr*, accounting for 32% of the total, followed by *qnrS* (26%). For example, in a study of

E. coli and *Klebsiella spp.* non-susceptible to Ciprofloxacin which were separated from Kenyan hospital discharged children under five, 20% of the isolates had *qnrB* co-carriage with *aac(6')-lb-cr*. Additionally, at least one PMQR gene among *qnrB*, *qnrS*, *aac(6')lb-cr*, *oqxAB*, and *qepA*, was detected in more than 80% of the isolates [69]. Similarly, in a cross-sectional investigation from March 2017 to July 2018, 90.5% of the isolates of fluoroquinolone-resistant Gram-negative bacteria from pediatric rectal swabs at a hospital in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, had one or more PMQR genes [70]. According to testing for fluoroquinolone resistance, most prevalent PMQR genes were *qnrB1* (40%) and *aac(6')-lb-cr* (74%). *Citrobacter spp.* had the greatest resistance rate (100%), followed by *K. pneumoniae* (76.1%), *E. coli* (65.6%), and *Enterobacter spp.* (31.9%). These results imply that children with hospital-acquired illnesses who are released from hospitals could act as community carriers of fluoroquinolone resistance. In a study on bloodstream at the University Teaching Hospital in Lusaka, Zambia, infections caused by AMR Gram-negative bacteria were found to contain the PMQR determinants *qnrA*, *qnrB* and *qnrS* in 25%, 20%, and 12% of the isolates, respectively. PCR analysis also confirmed multiple gene combinations such as *qnrA-qnrB* (5%), *qnrB-qnrS* (4%), and *qnrA-qnrS* (2%) [71].

Several studies on animals have also been conducted, one of which identified PMQR genes on multiresistant plasmids in *E. coli* isolates from the gastrointestinal tracts of 17 dogs from rural areas of central Angola [72]. Another study on *E. coli* isolates from poultry in North Central Nigeria detected PMQR genes *gyrA*, *qnrS1*, *qnrS2*, *qnrS11* and *qnrS13* [73].

PMQR in South America:

In a nationwide survey conducted in Argentina based on a set of 1,058 clinical enterobacteria [74], *oqxA* and *oqxB* were 0.4%, *qnr* genes were 3.9%, and with *aac(6')-lb-cr* was 4.6% prevalent, making the overall prevalence of PMQR genes 8.1%. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Q1130, which was isolated from the urine of a female patient aged 78 in 2007, was found to contain the hitherto unidentified PMQR gene *qnrE1* as a result of this investigation [75]. The presence of *qnrE1* in a clinical isolate of *Salmonella* Typhimurium- S. I 4,[5],12:i was also observed in another inquiry into 789 non-typhoidal *Salmonella enterica* strains recovered between 2000 and 2019 from human illnesses in São Paulo, Brazil [76].

Studies on AMR genetic elements in *E. coli* isolated from aquatic ecosystems have utilized several fish species that produce food to illustrate their significance in transmitting AMR to humans. PMQR genes, such as *qnrA* (25.0%) and *qnrB* (12.5%), were found primarily in farmed fish in one investigation on isolates of *E. coli* resistant to quinolones from fish farms and *Arapirama gigas*, a significant species of fish in the Brazilian Amazon river [77].

PMQR in North America:

Reports of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance from North America mainly comes from studies on animals and birds, including detection of 21.8% in the enrofloxacin-resistant *E. coli* isolates obtained from sick pigs in its United States between 2006 and 2016 included PMQR genes *qnrB2*, *qnrB77*, *qnrS1*, *qnrS2*, & *aac-(6)-lb'-cr* [78]. According to a different study on fecal swabs of American crows and common ravens roosting in Canada, birds may be AMR vectors. The PMQR genes *qnrB19*, *qnrC*, *qnrS1*, *oqxAB*, & *aac(6')-lb-cr* were found in *E. coli*

& one strain of *K. pneumoniae* [79]. Furthermore, one sample out of 516 isolates of *E. coli* from dog urine acquired from a diagnostic laboratory in Saskatoon, Canada, has been identified to contain the *aac(6')-Ib-cr* PMQR gene [80].

PMQR in Europe:

There has been several reports about discovery of PMQR genes in several European countries, among which one study involving ESBL/Carbapenemase-producing & antibiotic-resistant Gram-negative isolates in surface water sources in Northern Germany detected *qnrS1* & *aac(6')Ib-cr* genes in *E. coli*, and *qnrS1*, *oqxA*, *oqxB*, *aac(6')Ib-cr* in *K. pneumoniae* [81]. Similarly, bacterial strains isolated from four aquatic fisheries lowland salted lakes in Romania were shown to contain the PMQR markers *qnrA*, *qnrB*, and *qnrS* [82]. Furthermore, WGS Analysis of ciprofloxacin-resistant *Salmonella enterica* clinical isolates from Warsaw, Poland, revealed the presence of *qnrB19*, *qnrB36*, *qnrB67*, *qnrB82*, and *qnrS1* (2%) [83].

PMQR-containing Enterobacteriaceae isolates have been collected between 2013 and 2014 in 12 European countries viz. Germany, The Netherlands, Belgium, Hungary, Poland, Sweden, Czech Republic, Switzerland, France, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom, through ComPath, which is an antimicrobial resistance monitoring program in Bacterial pathogens found in sick cats and dogs [84]. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* harbouring *qnrB* & *qnrS*, along with *Enterobacter cloacae* carrying *qnrB*, have also been isolated from dogs in Austria [85]. Another study in western Romania, on 147 *E. coli* strains recovered from humans along with 53 from pigs revealed the *qnrS* gene in 13 human subjects and all swine samples, *qnrB* gene in 9 human and all the swine isolates, and *qnrA* gene in only 3 of the human isolates, but not in pigs [86]. A similar study on 214 non-repetitive Enterobacteriaceae strains from urine clinical isolates collected at Semmelweis University in Budapest, Hungary, detected *oqxAB*, *aac(6')-Ib-cr*, *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrD*, & *qnrS* genes [87].

Overall impact of PMQR:

PMQR significantly impacts clinical outcomes by increasing resistance to quinolones, a class of antibiotics crucial for treating various bacterial infections. This resistance mechanism not only affects the activity of quinolones but also complicates treatment regimens, leading to potential treatment failures and increased healthcare burden. PMQR genes are frequently identified in various *Enterobacteriaceae*, like *Salmonella*, *Proteus*, *E. coli*, & *K. pneumoniae* [88-90]. Plasmids which may be passed from one bacterium to another contain PMQR genes, enhancing the spread of resistance across different species and environments [88, 91]. Infections caused by PMQR-positive bacteria, such as those in patients with inflammatory bowel disease or sepsis, may lead to more severe disease outcomes and limit the effectiveness of quinolone therapy [90, 92]. Global public health is seriously threatened by the widespread dissemination of PMQR genes, since it can result in outbreaks of resistant infections in healthcare settings and the community [91]. Monitoring and controlling the spread of PMQR genes are thus crucial for maintaining the efficacy of quinolones and ensuring successful treatment outcomes [90, 91]. While PMQR significantly contributes to quinolone resistance, it is important to consider other resistance mechanisms that contribute to the overall resistance landscape, including efflux pumps and chromosomal alterations.

Future perspectives:

Although several potential therapeutic intervention strategies to combat PMQR have been proposed over the past few years, including combining quinolones with agents that inhibit the mechanisms of resistance, such as efflux pump inhibitors [93] or SOS response suppressors [94], the rapid evolution of resistance mechanisms requires further research to develop effective interventions against PMQR. Some of the prospective approaches might involve-

- small molecule inhibitors or peptides that bind Qnr proteins and prevent them from shielding DNA gyrase/topoisomerase IV from quinolones,
- enzyme inhibitors to block the acetyltransferase activity of AAC(6')-Ib-cr,
- CRISPR-Cas systems engineered to selectively target and cleave resistance plasmids,
- antisense oligonucleotides or RNA interference (RNAi) to silence *qnr*, *aac(6')-Ib-cr*, or efflux pump genes,
- engineered or natural bacteriophages that preferentially infect PMQR-harboring strains or deliver compounds that destabilize or inhibit plasmid replication.

Nevertheless, some researchers argue that focusing solely on PMQR may undermine the broader context of antibiotic resistance, which involves multiple factors including environmental influences and patient management practices. Hence they emphasize more on antibiotic stewardship programs to minimize quinolone overuse and reduce selective pressure, and employing diagnostic-guided therapy to avoid empirical quinolone use. Other probable strategies would be to develop next-generation quinolones less susceptible to PMQR and modification of molecular structures to evade acetylation or efflux.

Conclusion:

Plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance is a well-described phenomenon that has become a widespread problem across the world, and especially in the developing countries, since quinolones are widely utilized in veterinary and human medicine, as well as in animal husbandry, specifically poultry production. There is mounting evidence linking the rise in antimicrobial resistance between animals and humans, particularly for common foodborne pathogens resistant to quinolones, thereby becoming a significant One Health issue. Novel approaches for controlling the rising threat of PMQR has therefore become the need of the hour and demands urgent attention from the global scientific community.

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Supplementary Information

Table S1: Summary of research articles cited in the Discussion section of this review.

Serial No.	Continent	Country	PMQR genes identified	Citation	PubMed ID	
1	Asia	India	<i>qnrS1</i>	<i>Singh et al, 2022</i>	35343419	
2			<i>qnrB, qnrS</i>	<i>Sivakumar et al, 2021</i>	33746253	
3			<i>qnrB, qnrS</i>	<i>Mallick et al, 2024</i>	39367887	
4		China	<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, oqxA, oqxB, qnrS2</i>	<i>Hu et al, 2021</i>	34211439	
5			<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, oqxA, oqxB</i>	<i>Hu et al, 2022</i>	36160190	
6			<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, oqxAB, qnrS, qnrA, qnrB, qnrD, qnrVC</i>	<i>Sun et al, 2024</i>	38747582	
7			<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, qnrA, qnrB, qnrD, qnrS, oqxB</i>	<i>Zhao et al, 2024</i>	38757951	
8			<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, qnrS, oqxAB, qnrC, qnrD</i>	<i>Li et al, 2025</i>	38669052	
9			Bangladesh	<i>qnrS, qepA</i>	<i>Rahman et al, 2017</i>	29075330
10		<i>aac(6')-bl-cr, oqxAB, qnrB, qepA</i>		<i>Amin et al, 2021</i>	34965260	
11		Thailand	<i>aac(6')-bl-cr, qepA, oqxAB</i>	<i>Tabut et al, 2022</i>	36551417	
13			<i>qnrS</i>	<i>Chantharothaiphachit et al, 2022</i>	35156609	
14		Philippines	<i>qnrA1, qnrB4, qnrS1</i>	<i>Belotindos et al, 2021</i>	33918946	
15		Iran	<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, oqxB, oqxA, qnrB, qnrS, qnrD, qepA, qnrA, qnrC</i>	<i>Azargun et al, 2019</i>	30445211	
16		Iraq	<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, qnrB, qepA, qnrS</i>	<i>Kareem et al, 2021</i>	33603418	
17		Saudi Arabia	<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, qnrS</i>	<i>Ibrahim, 2023</i>	38264897	
18		Africa	Kenya	<i>aac(6')lb-cr, qnrB, oqxAB, qnrS, qepA</i>	<i>Kariuki et al, 2023</i>	37173674
19			Tanzania	<i>aac(6')-lb-cr, qnrB1, qnrB6, qnrS1, oqx</i>	<i>Kibwana et al, 2023</i>	36882712
20			Zambia	<i>qnrA, qnrB, qnrS</i>	<i>Yamba et al, 2023</i>	36963041
21			Angola	<i>qepA, qnrS1, qnrB19, aac(6')-Ib-cr</i>	<i>Albrechtova et al, 2014</i>	24568119

22		Nigeria	<i>qnrS1, qnrS2, qnrS11, qnrS13</i>	<i>Al-Mustapha et al, 2023</i>	36738714
23	South America	Argentina	<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr, qnrB2, qnrB10, qnrB19, oqxA, oqxB</i>	<i>Albornoz et al, 2017</i>	27728774
24			<i>qnrE1</i>	<i>Albornoz et al, 2017</i>	28193666
25		Brazil	<i>qnrE1</i>	<i>Calarga et al, 2022</i>	35446010
26			<i>qnrA, qnrB</i>	<i>Lima et al, 2022</i>	35456858
27	North America	USA	<i>qnrB77, qnrB2, qnrS1, qnrS2, aac(6)-Ib'-cr</i>	<i>Hayer et al, 2020</i>	33115839
28		Canada	<i>qnrS1, qnrB19, qnrC, oqxAB, aac(6')-Ib-cr</i>	<i>Janecko et al, 2018</i>	29675942
29			<i>aac(6')-Ib-cr</i>	<i>Courtice et al, 2021</i>	33751667
30	Europe	Germany	<i>oqxA, oqxB, qnrS1, aac(6')Ib-cr</i>	<i>Falgenhauer et al, 2019</i>	31849911
31		Romania	<i>qnrA, qnrB, qnrS</i>	<i>Lazăr et al, 2021</i>	33499841
32			<i>qnrS, qnrB, qnrA</i>	<i>Doma et al, 2020</i>	33066610
33		Poland	<i>qnrB19, qnrB36, qnrB67, qnrB82, qnrS1</i>	<i>Piekarska et al, 2023</i>	36839465
34		Austria	<i>qnrB, qnrS</i>	<i>Loncaric et al, 2020</i>	32645942
35		Hungary	<i>qnrA, qnrB, qnrD, qnrS, aac(6')-Ib-cr, oqxAB</i>	<i>Szabó et al, 2018</i>	29471688